

Solvent Effects on the Stability Constants of the Molecular Complexes of Chloranil with Benzoic and Salicylic Acids

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In order to explore the role of solvents on the molecular complexes, the stability or the formation constants of the molecular complexes of chloranil with benzoic and salicylic acids have been determined in different solvents. The stability constants of the complexes are high indicating fairly stable complex formation resulting from both specific (i.e. chemical) and non-specific (i.e. physical) interactions. The formation constants for the benzoic acid complexes are higher in aromatic solvents but lower in aliphatic solvents but the reverse has been found to be true in case of salicylic acid complexes. The intramolecular hydrogen bonding in case of salicylic acid may be the reasons for the changes in chemical and physical interactions. The correlations of ΔG_s° of the complexes against $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ and ΔG_s° against E_T (30) (solvent polarity) have been attempted to understand the role of solvents with limited success.

Various theoretical attempts^{1,2} have been made to understand the specific nature of solvation but the problem eludes solution as the solvation phenomenon is not exactly defined and also the standard states will differ with solvents. But experimental attempts may be made to determine the variation of the equilibrium constants with solvents and try to correlate the variation of Gibbs energy changes of the complexes with solvent properties. This led us to determine the molecular complexes of two structurally related compounds like benzoic and salicylic acids with chloranil, an well-known acceptor, in different solvents.

Results and Discussion

The equilibrium constants (K_c) for the complex between donor (D) (benzoic acid or salicylic acid) and acceptor (A) (chloranil),

can be written as

$$K_c = \frac{[AD] \gamma_{AD}}{[A][D] \gamma_A \gamma_D} \quad (2)$$

where, γ_{AD} , γ_A and γ_D are the activity coefficients of AD, A and D respectively.

In view of the non-electrolytic characters of A, D and AD and at very low concentrations of A and D, the ratio $\gamma_{AD}/\gamma_A \gamma_D$ in the non-aqueous solvents like benzene or chloroform can be reasonably regarded to be unity.

The usual practice of taking $D \gg A$ has been avoided and instead equivalent concentrations of D and A (10^{-3} to 10^{-4} M) have been utilised. Since both D and AD absorb in the region of study, Benesi-Hildebrand³⁻⁵ equation or Scott equation⁶ could not be utilised. Rather, an iterative procedure⁷ for the calculation of the equilibrium constant has been adopted. The expression is

$$\frac{C_1}{d_2 - d_1} = \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)l} + \frac{1}{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)(C_2 - x)l} K \quad (l = 1 \text{ cm}) \quad (3)$$

where, $d_1 = \epsilon_1 C_1 l$

$$d_2 = \epsilon_1 \lambda l + \epsilon_1 (C_1 - x)l = \epsilon_1 C_1 l + (\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1) \lambda l \quad (5)$$

where C_1 , d_1 , ϵ_1 and x , d_2 and ϵ_2 are the concentration, absorptivity and molar absorptivity of chloranil and the complex respectively. C_2 is the concentration of the acid which does not absorb in the region under study. Initially, x is supposed to be small, the plot of $C_1/(d_2 - d_1)$ against $1/C_2$ has been made to get approximate values of x . The values of λ have now been utilised to get refined values of K_c , $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and x . The iteration has been repeated till constant values of $1/(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)$ and K have been obtained. Generally, two to three iterations are sufficient to get the constant values. The molar absorptivities of the complexes and the equilibrium constants are given in Table 1. However, the method, though gives the accurate values of K , but the values of ϵ_2 can only be regarded to be approximate.

Most of the equilibrium constant values determined optically have been calculated using one of the components in large excess. The results are likely to be vitiated due to possible formation of termolecular complexes and of isomeric complexes, specific solvation and particularly if the components also absorb in the region. Comparison of the results from the determinations of association constant (K) of the charge transfer complexes under various conditions and using different methods led Foster^{3,8} to conclude that more weight should be given to K values obtained from optical data under conditions $(D)_c = (A)_c$ and to K values from nmr chemical shift data, regarded to be the best method for the determination of K . In case of nmr method, the position of the magnetic resonance absorption of a particular nucleus will be a time-averaged resultant of its behaviour in the different environments and the contributions of the ternary complexes, if any, can be well-reflected and taken into account in the measured chemical shift δ . The method appears to be the best method of de-

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF DONOR-ACCEPTOR COMPLEX IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AT 298 K

Solvents	λ_{\max} nm	Benzoic acid-Chloranil			Salicylic acid-Chloranil		
		$\epsilon_2 \times 10^{-2}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$	K_{AD} $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\epsilon_2 \times 10^{-2}$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{m}^{-1}$	K_{AD} $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}
Benzene	336	2454.7	230.6	13.48	1857	144	12.32
Toluene	360	2677.7	224.3	13.41	2608	143	12.31
<i>o</i> -Xylene	388	270.4	233.1	13.51	110	156	12.51
Methyl	370	381.1	139.6	12.24	607	206	13.19
Dichloromethane	377	264.4	114.4	11.75	891	196	13.08
Chloroform	374	69.2	119.5	11.85	602	183	12.91
Carbon tetrachloride	370	349.6	125.0	11.96	449	180	12.87

termination of K . Thus, the K_c values determined by us using $(D)_c = (A)_c$ can be regarded to be accurate.

The equilibrium constants as given in Table 1 show appreciable solvent dependence. However, solute-solvent interaction is an universal phenomenon in all solvation processes. Thus, the formation of complexes between A or D with solvents to form [AS] or [DS] can not be ruled out. CT complex formation between chloranil with solvents like benzene, chloroform etc. in heptane and their equilibrium constants have been reported^{9,10}. The true values^{2,3} of the equilibrium constants can be written as

$$K_{\text{correct.d}}^{AD} = K_{\text{observed}}^{AD} \left[1 + K_s^{\text{AS}}[\text{S}] \right] \left[1 + K_s^{\text{DS}}[\text{S}] \right] \quad (6)$$

In the present investigation, the effect of complex formation between chloranil with solvents can be considered to be eliminated as the blank solutions contained chloranil in the respective solvents under study and the effect has been taken into consideration in the calculation. It is not possible to ascribe the nature of the interactions in the formation of the complexes. Chloranil is known to form strong CT complexes with π -electron donors like benzene or toluene but the possibility of the formation of such complexes^{9,10} of chloranil with aliphatic solvents is small. Moreover, the equilibrium or association constants for the CT complexes of chloranil with π -electron donor^{9,10} are low whereas the equilibrium constant between chloranil with benzoic or salicylic acids obtained by us are high indicating that the complexes are fairly stable and it is expected that both specific i.e. chemical interaction (like charge transfer with π -donors, hydrogen bonding,

and non-specific i.e. physical interactions (like dispersion interactions, etc.) are involved in the formation of com-

plexes. Intramolecular hydrogen bonding in case of salicylic acid may have some effect on the hydrogen bond formation.

The molar absorptivities of the complexes (Table 1) are fairly high, the ϵ values are usually higher for benzoic acid complexes in aromatic solvents but lower in case of aliphatic solvents and they are exactly reverse in case of salicylic acid complexes. The solvent effect on the association constants of chloranil + benzoic acid and chloranil + salicylic acid complexes as given in Table 1, shows that the formation constants for the benzoic acid complexes are higher in aromatic solvents but lower in aliphatic solvents, whereas the reverse has been found to be true in case of salicylic acid complexes.

However, the sequence of the association constants of the benzoic acid complexes in different aliphatic solvents is: $K_{\text{CCl}_4} > K_{\text{CHCl}_3} > K_{\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2}$. The results are in agreement with the observed order of K for association between neutral donors and neutral acceptors^{11,12}. But the order is reversed in case of salicylic acid complexes. The reasons for the differences, though difficult to suggest, may be as follows. (i) Formation of n-mers (usually dimers) has different association constant values for benzoic acid and salicylic acid. The aspect of self-association of the component species¹³ has not been taken into account but for minimising the association processes, dilute solutions of both A and D have been used with $[\text{D}] \approx [\text{A}]$. (ii) Due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding, association between salicylic acid may be different from that of benzoic acid and hydrogen bonding capabilities of benzoic and salicylic acids are different. (iii) Differences in the dispersion interactions are due to the change in the dipole moments of the acids.

The real understanding of solvent effect is difficult and in spite of enormous work, nothing positive has emerged. However, some useful information can be derived from the consideration of the solvation cycle for the transfer processes of the reactions from the gas phase (g) to solution (s),

$$\Delta E_{D, \text{ solv.}} = \Delta E_D(\text{CH}) + \Delta E_D(\text{PH})$$

where, (i) $\Delta E_D(\text{CH})$ is the energy due to the formation of the complex $(\text{D, S}_p)_s$ arising from specific or chemical interactions and (ii) $\Delta E_D(\text{PH})$ is the energy due to physical or non-specific interactions of the complex with solvent S. The expression holds good for $\Delta E_{A, \text{ solv.}}$, $\Delta E_{DA, \text{ solv.}}$.

For a particular (DA) complex in different solvents, chemical interactions between D and A can be regarded to be constant. The solvent effect arises mainly from the differences in non-specific interactions. ΔE_g values are not known but must be considerably different from ΔE_s . The cycle can be written simply as

$$\Delta E_s = \Delta E_g + [\Delta E_{DA}(\text{PH}) - \Delta E_D(\text{PH}) - \Delta E_A(\text{PH})]$$

The non-specific solvation has been assumed to be the summation of two parts²: (i) ΔE^d , energy of dispersion interactions and (ii) ΔE^e energy of electrostatic interactions. In case of (DA) complexes studied, ΔE^e part should change due to change in ϵ values but the main contribution arises from dispersion interactions. For benzoic and salicylic acid complexes in a particular solvent, the difference in ΔG values arises from the differences in chemical interactions arising from intramolecular hydrogen bonding in salicylic acid; ΔE^e should likely to be the same but variation in ΔE^d may arise.

For better understanding of the solvation effect^{2,14,15} the following expression has been utilised,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_s &= \Delta G_g + \Delta G^d - A \Delta \mu^2 \frac{\epsilon - 1}{2\epsilon + 1} \\ &= \Delta G_g + G^d + \beta \frac{(\epsilon - 1)}{(2\epsilon + 1)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } A = \frac{4\pi\Delta^2}{3} \text{ and } \Delta\mu^2 = \frac{\mu_{DA}^2}{V_{DA}} - \frac{\mu_D^2}{V_D} - \frac{\mu_A^2}{V_A}$$

V and $\Delta\mu$ represent molar volume and the reaction polarity, μ_D , μ_A and μ_{DA} are the dipole moments, $\beta = -A\Delta\mu^2$.

Assuming ΔE^d to depend weakly on the solvents, the plot of ΔG_s against $f(\epsilon) = (\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ should be straight

line. However, two distinct lines, one for the aromatic solvents and other for the aliphatic solvents have been obtained. Deviation has been found in case of benzoic acid complexes in acetonitrile. ΔG^d appears to be different for aromatic and aliphatic solvents.

For benzoic and salicylic acid complexes in aromatic solvents, the slopes have been found to be negative, i.e. ($\Delta\mu^2$ positive) indicating the fairly strong polar complex formation. In aliphatic solvents, benzoic acid forms moderately strong polar complexes (slope negative, i.e. β positive) but the slope for salicylic acid complexes in aliphatic solvents are slightly positive, i.e. $\Delta\mu^2$ negative indicating weakly polar complex formation. It is apparent that the dipole moment of benzoic acid-chloranil complex is considerably different from that of salicylic acid-chloranil complex. The non-linear dependence of ΔG on $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ is characteristic of complexes of intermediate bond energy in which intramolecular equilibrium of proton transfer²

takes place. Here solvent-induced changes of complex dipole moment are possible. Thus, the correlation of ΔG against $f(\epsilon)$ has been found to be good.

The differences between aliphatic solvents (studied here) and aromatic solvents arise from hydrogen bonding capability of the solvents. CH_2Cl_2 , CHCl_3 and CH_3CN , CCl_4 are known to be π -electron acceptors whereas CH_3CN may act as lone electron pair donor.

Attempts have also been made to correlate ΔG against solvent polarity $E_T(30)$ ¹⁶⁻¹⁸. The variation of the plot of ΔG against E_T are similar to the plots of ΔG vs $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ with slight variation. Thus, it is apparent that the empirical parameter 'solvent polarity' as defined by Dimroth-Reichardt's¹⁶⁻¹⁸ $E_T(30)$ (based on the transition of pyridinium or phenolate betaine) or Z -value of Kosower¹⁹ (based on the transition of 1-ethyl-4-methoxycarbonylpyridinium iodide) are hardly better than other solvent parameters like ϵ , $(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)$ and μ . $E_T(30)$ or Z values are dependent on the transition from the ground state to the excited states - the standard states of which are not well-defined and vary with the solvent systems. It can not take into account all specific interactions like H-bonded electron pair donor acceptor (HBD/HBA, EPD/EPA), solvophobic interactions and non-specific interactions like inductive, dispersing and coulombic interactions for which they stand for. Moreover, no idea regarding different types of interactions like coulombic, dipolar or dispersion interactions can be obtained from correlations of ΔG against solvent polarity. Thus, their utility in the correlation of equilibrium constants with solvent polarity is limited.

Experimental

Chloranil (AnalaR), benzoic acid and salicylic acid

(G. R., E. Merck) were used as such. Benzene, toluene, *o*-xylene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, dichloroethane, acetonitrile were of spectroscopic quality (Sisco, India). The solvents were distilled before use.

Different concentrations were mixed and allowed to come to equilibrium and the absorption measurements were made with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. All measurements were done at 298 K using freshly prepared solutions.

Benzoic acid, salicylic acid and chloranil are known to absorb strongly in the uv region (200 – 400 nm). The formation of complexes between the acids and chloranil is also accompanied by the spectral changes. Thus, conspicuous charge-transfer bands of the complexes are difficult to obtain in the uv-region due to superimposition of absorption curves of the complexes and the components and the CT bands may not be the true bands as well. Therefore, the

Fig. 1. Spectra in chloroform : (O) chloranil, (□) chloranil + benzoic acid and (●) chloranil + salicylic acid; [chloranil] = [benzoic acid] = [salicylic acid] = 2.0×10^{-3} M.

complexes were studied in the region above 320 nm where absorption due to acids may be eliminated and the absorptions are due to chloranil and the complexes. The complex formation between chloranil with benzoic acid and salicylic acid in chloroform and benzene is shown in Fig. 1.

References

1. J. F. COETZEE and C. D. RITCHIE, "Solute-solvent Interactions", Dekker, New York, 1969.
2. J. MAŁECKI in "Molecular Interactions", 3rd. ed., H. RATAJCZAK and W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, Wiley, New York, 1982, Chap. 4.
3. R. FOSTER, "Organic Charge-Transfer Complexes", Academic, London, 1969.
4. R. FOSTER, "Molecular Complexes", Elek Science, London, 1974, Vol. 2, Chap. 3.
5. H. A. BENESI and J. H. HILDERBRAND, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2703.
6. R. L. SCOTT, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Phys-Bas*, 1956, 75, 787.
7. K. MAJUMDER, K. K. MAJUMDER and S. C. LAHIRI, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 1990, 46, 1137.
8. Ref. 3, p. 179.
9. B. B. BHOWMIK and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 1986, 42, 1217, 1361.
10. B. B. BHOWMIK and A. BHATTACHARYYA, *Spectrochim Acta, Part A*, 1988, 44, 1147.
11. R. FOSTER and D. U. HAMMICK, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2685.
12. C. C. THOMSON, JR. and P. A. D. DE MAINE *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3096; *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1965, 69, 2766.
13. D. W. TANNER and J. C. BRANICE, *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1966, 70, 3816.
14. L. ONSAGER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1486.
15. C. J. F. BOTTCHER, "Theory of Electric Polarisation", Elsevier, Amsterdam.
16. K. DIMROTH and C. REICHARDT, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1966, 215, 344.
17. C. REICHARDT, "Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", Verlag Chemie, Weinheim, 1979.
18. C. REICHARDT in "Molecular Complexes", ed. H. RATAJCZAK and W. J. ORVILLE-THOMAS, Wiley, New York, 1984, Vol. 3, Chap. 5.
19. E. M. KOSOWER, "An Introduction to Physical Organic Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1968.